

Country	Continent	COUNTA de Title
Australia	Oceania	3
Austria	Europe	2
Belgium	Europe	3
Canada	North America	1
China	Asia	6
Colombia	South America	1
Estonia	Europe	1
Germany	Europe	2
Indonesia	Asia	8
Italy	Europe	5
Malawi	Africa	1
Malaysia	Asia	2
Morocco	Africa	2
Namibia	Africa	1
Netherlands	Europe	1
Norway	Europe	1
Romania	Europe	1
Saudi Arabia	Asia	1
Slovenia	Europe	1
South Korea	Asia	1
Spain	Europe	3
Switzerland	Europe	1
Thailand	Asia	2
Uganda	Africa	1
United Arab Emir	Asia	1
United Kingdom	Europe	2
Uruguay	South America	1
USA	North America	8

Year	COUNT de Year
1996	1
2002	2
2003	1
2004	1
2009	1
2010	2
2011	2
2012	3
2014	2
2015	3
2016	4
2017	4
2018	3
2019	3
2020	3
2021	2
2022	5
2023	6
2024	4
2025	11
Total geral	63

Continent	SUM de COUNT
Africa	5
Asia	21
Europe	23
North America	9
Oceania	3
South America	2
Total geral	63